

ART STUDIES

ARTISTIC AND DESIGN COMPETENCE TRAINING OF A VOCATIONAL EDUCATOR IN THE FIELD

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ABSTRACT

The development of science and technology in today's world affects breakthroughs in all areas of society. Art design occupies a predominant place in human life and work and is becoming a necessary part of the new reality.

The relevance of the problem of training art design teachers lies in the increasing need of education for competent teachers-designers with professional skills that meet modern demands. Modern education means renewal and modernization of educational systems and the use of digital, innovative technologies and methods. International experience introduces digital learning or interdisciplinary approach to increase educational motivation for high results in the educational process.

Renewal of the education system to a new approach, where it is necessary to modernise the conditions that ensure the effectiveness and quality of the training of an art design teacher.

The aim of the study is to consider the art and design aspect of the art design teacher's activity, which is a disciplinary composition, with theoretical substantiation of the structural and content model of teaching art competence and planning the professional training of the art design teacher.

Keywords: art design, design educator, education, competence, art and design competence, integration, interdisciplinarity, modernisation.

Introduction

Design in modern society occupies a special place in human life and activity. In order to form highly professional specialists, it is necessary to update the educational environment to meet the individual characteristics of the learner and reflect the specifics of future professional activities. Modern education as a space of free creative communication, in all spheres of activity acquires a project nature [1]. Professional training of students in higher education institutions should meet the requirements of new trends in the field of art design, which is a reflection of continuous implementation of professional activity [2].

Art design is a modern form of project and design creativity. Art design is a creative-combinatorial process that combines the acquired knowledge to solve emerging problems and realise new ideas, setting stereotypical ideas back and reacting subtly to the changes taking place. The system of professional competences forms and ensures the level of an art designer in accordance with the mastered specialisation. Art-designer should have the formed professional competences to carry out quality professional activity. The ability to analyse and foresee fast-changing and fast-developing social and economic market situations [3]. The competence is the ability, knowledge and skills, applying on the basis of practical experience, to solve to solve professional tasks [4]. Competence or competences is a narrower, more atomistic notion that directly relates to

specific criteria and standards, such as efficient or high-quality performance of artistic and design work [5]. Highly qualified professionals contribute highly to competitiveness and participate in the process of continuous educational improvement [6].

The formation and development of competences takes place through learning and learner feedback, i.e. reflection. Each learner perceives information differently, so there are individual forms and methods of learning. The focus is on the development of artistic and design competences, which are essential for enhancing creative skills [7]. Art-design education is carried out through art design, methods and means of learning [8]. Relevant competences to be possessed by students are determined by the expected outcomes at the stages of the educational process [9].

The research focuses on the requirement of current trends defining the quality of competency-based approaches in the development of the new generation of state educational standards [10]

The basic principle of the training of art design educators is the principle of lifelong learning [11]. The design education system relies on this principle at the following levels: pre-university training, initial, secondary vocational training, higher vocational education and postgraduate education (professional development during practical activities). Design-education shall provide:

1. training a future specialist, with a creative method of thinking, with a high level of culture in professional creative activity;
 2. training a future specialist capable of designing the material and spatial environment.
 3. to develop a specialist on the basis of an interdisciplinary [12].
 4. to master the skills of artistic and design modeling based on a systematic and competent approach to solving design problems in the interaction of social, functional, technical, economic, artistic and compositional factors;
 5. the ability to design and take into account the conditions of modern production, the use of new technologies and efficient materials [13];
- Professional training in design is :

- the social relevance and professionalism of design work.
- The study of the basic laws and theories of the development of science, art, etc.
- mastering computer technology, tools, platforms, project graphics, learning the history of visual arts and mastering practical skills;
- implementation skills and shaping of practical activities [14]

Methods

On the basis of professional, information-technical, communicative mobility and the ability of creative self-realization, future specialists form prospective competences in the labour market. The peculiarity of specific design activity is mastering professional skill and learning design theory, the ability to successfully apply knowledge in art and design activity [15]

Table 1.

Competence of a vocational teacher (design)

Competence of a vocational teacher (design)	General cultural competences	General science		
		Socio-communicative		
		Personal		
		Instrumental		
	Professional competences	General vocational		
		Professionally-specialised	Artistic and design competence	Formed artistic and design competence

The formation of art and design competence involves a creative process in the interaction between art, science and technology. The competence of art and design creativity, the ability to engage successfully and effectively in design creativity, encompasses a wide

range of knowledge, skills as well as attitudes and values. Building competence in design creativity requires the development of such knowledge, skills, as well as attitudes and values [16].

Table 2.

The components of art-project competence

Artistic and design competence	Personal	Awareness of the social significance of design activity and the professional responsibility of the designer, to cultivate the qualities that ensure the successful performance of artistic and design activities	Developed imaginative, constructive thinking, abstract-logical thinking, spatial thinking and imagination, creativity, emotional stability, self-organisation, self-control; understanding the prospects of their future activities, the ability to be guided by the predictions of the sciences (architecture, design, psychology, pedagogy, etc.)
	Artistic	The ability to reproduce designed objects by art-imaginative means, based on an analytical, aesthetic and practical attitude towards the cultural and artistic values of works of fine art	Mastering the methods of pictorial language of drawing and painting; mastering the basics of artistic composition; mastering the skills of depicting the objective world, space and the human figure; mastering demonstration methods of depicting design objects, as well as realising the role of artistic and pictorial creativity in mastering the object component
	Project	The ability to design the material and spatial environment for developing work, domestic and social life processes according to the laws of expediency and beauty	Mastery of design skills, including knowledge of basic compositional concepts, how to achieve perceptual integrity and expressiveness of the design concept; mastery of design methods, ability to apply graphical knowledge and skills to develop drawings according to regulatory requirements, mastery of information computer technology

The general didactic concept of the integrity of the learning and educational process requires an integrated

and sound approach to all components of each discipline of objectives, content, methods, means and

organisational forms of learning, which together and in interconnection form a system of professional learning.

In exploring the problem of the relationship between science and the discipline in the process of defining learning content, it is important to consider the components of the science being studied, its foundations, theories, laws and regularities, methods, ideas, and principles. While the complexity of this problem is considerable at the stage of selecting and adjusting teaching material, the compilation of textbooks and teaching aids should be solved in the course of the work process. This approach makes it possible to combine didactic interrelated but conflicting principles of scientific and accessible learning [17] The activity of a professional education teacher in the field of design should have a significant integrative potential, where two integrative systems are combined: pedagogical system and professional system represented by design itself, which constitutes its polystructural organization. The stages of pedagogical integration have been developed in the scientific literature [18].

Methods

Apply their knowledge and skills directly to changing circumstances:

- Application of cognitive and metacognitive skills such as critical thinking, creative thinking, as well as self-regulation and self-education;
- Application of social and emotional skills such as empathy, self-efficacy and cooperation;
- Application of practical and physical skills, as well as the use of information and communication technology [19].

The overall didactic concept of the process of forming artistic design competence consists of four aspects of personal education:

- The desire for innovation, new social models, cooperation, adaptability, creativity, commitment and openness create new values.
- Competitive relevance, balance sheet compatibility.
- Responsibility for the result of the work, the ability to assess oneself externally.
- Independence in decision-making, etc. [20]

For the modern designer to develop professional training and competence in accordance with modern requirements, it will be effective to introduce a structure-content model into the training process [21]. In order to implement the structural-constructive model of formation of art-project competence the following conditions are necessary

- 1) the principle of integrating the disciplines by branch of study and specialised training;
- 2) study based on the major discipline and project-based content learning;
- 3) the learning process includes project-creative tasks and artistic orientations.

The quality of the educational process is synthesised by the functioning of the components, the activities of the actors, the quality of the educational programmes, the scientific and pedagogical qualifications of the staff, the conditions of the educa-

tional process (educational and methodological, scientific and methodological support, pedagogical technologies used), etc. [22]

The study of assessing the level of formation of students' art-project competence examines the model of functional management subsystems and identifies the management functions of these subsystems: motivational-targeting, planning, organizational-executive, control and diagnostic, information-analytical, regulatory-corrective, planning.

A subsystem is a parameter for evaluating pedagogical activities:

- Quality diagnostics in the disciplines of the art and design group;
- assessing the quality of teaching materials and curricula;
- assessing the quality of interdisciplinary links in teaching a group of art and design disciplines [23].

The diagnosis of the quality of the teaching process in the disciplines was based on the method of pedagogical observation, as a direct perception by the researcher of the pedagogical processes under study [24].

The study involved a holistic process of pedagogical observation (discrete observation). In continuous observation, the principle of neutrality was implemented (the researcher is not involved in real activities).

The following conclusions were drawn from the study of the pedagogical subsystems:

- The interdisciplinary links between the subjects of the art and design group have not been taken into account in the organisation of the learning process and the activities of the teachers
- The lack of interdisciplinary links and the emphasis on the major discipline had a negative impact on the integrity of the training[23];

To select sketches for an art and design project, you need to have the materials available:

- a description of each sketch and material option;
- a list of the literature and research materials needed for the project;
- sketches of layouts and models for the art and design project;
- a table of distribution of justifications;
- schematic tables of the project, etc.

The art and design project must meet the requirement and condition of the design brief [25]

Art competence is formed by studying the disciplines of art and creative cycle "Drawing", "Painting", "Composition", "History of Design", etc., and design competence - in the process of teaching the disciplines of design and creative cycle "Plastics", "Artistic designing", "Artistic modeling", etc. with full interdisciplinary linkage constitutes the basic professional education.

2. Definition of objectives. When defining objectives, a special point is to differentiate between external (formal) and internal (substantive) objectives. The external objectives are to save time, increase coherence (density of learning material), eliminate multi-subject and disciplinary parallelism, etc. The internal goals are the formation of neo-education, covering all areas of personal activity: cognitive, affective (emotional-

value) and psychomotor. In this way, two goals are defined:

1) the content of the training of a professional design teacher and the construction of an integrated framework

2) Based on disciplinary integration, the formation of professional competence (artistic and design competence) [26]

The practice of educational activities and scientific-pedagogical research becomes particularly relevant, in training specialists on the basis of innovative approaches. The notions of "knowledge", "abilities", "skills" are replaced by "competences", "competence", fixing on the competence approach in education. The analysis of the literature shows the ambiguity of interpretation as a systemic concept, to the pedagogical process. A successful solution is possible in case of fundamentally, different from traditional structuring of professional education content as professional competences [27].

In order to improve the effectiveness and quality of the educational process of teacher training, the following pedagogical objectives need to be set:

1) Integration and intensification of the educational process:

- Exploring interdisciplinary and inter-sectoral links (e.g. art history - costume history - design - artistic modelling - computer graphics - nanomaterials);

- Self-development of learners (development of creative and creative thinking, shaping and nurturing of aesthetic taste).

- Providing motivation, intensifying cognitive activity (tasks in the context of real art-project activities, the use of information technology and modern digital tools);

- the use of innovative teaching methods (individual and group; research, etc.)

2. Implementation of modern requirements in dynamically rapidly changing conditions - training of competent and creative professionals capable of implementing professional and pedagogical activities in the field of design [28].

3. definition of value-goal bases. As the leading value-target bases of the integrated structure, the training of a professional education teacher in design, competence approach to develop a holistic concept of professionalization, taking into account the above approaches and processes of integration of psychological and pedagogical, industry and production-technological knowledge.

Interdisciplinary interaction and mutual complementarity leads to the development of a professional personality and integration possessing:

- Take responsibility for the values of national and universal cultures, expressing spiritual competence

- social competence, civic maturity;

- moral and ethical competence - carrying out one's duties with integrity and quality;

- psycho-physiological competence, the performance of their professional duties;

- individual competence - a set of qualities, characteristics of a person (style of activity);

- special competence, knowledge, abilities, skills, for the type of activity mastered;

- forward-looking competence - reacting to the changing situation in the field of professional activity.

Competences are the knowledge, skills and personal qualities for successful activities in a particular field. Competence-based approach ensures the quality of education, formation of professionally competent, competitive specialist. Competency-based and systemic approaches, interdisciplinary interaction, and integration principles are the tools of modern professional education development. [29]. The heuristic-technological symbiosis forms a specialist of integral profile, capable of carrying out universal-functional activity. Intensively able to concentrate and implement specific tasks.

Competence-based technology in vocational education: organisational, technical, technological and mobilisation skills development.

The principle of consistency and continuity in mastering the profession of a professional education teacher is a value-aimed basis for building an integrated content structure of professional education teacher training in the field of design. The system approach to training organization in interdisciplinary interaction, providing integration of the content of academic disciplines, holistic consideration of the problem of professional competence development, taking into account integration processes, for successful formation of professional competences [30].

4. identifying a systemic factor. Monocentric integration is the core of the training content. The three pillars of training content - psycho-pedagogical, artistic and project-based - the core is psycho-pedagogical. Artistic and project-based content contains demonstration material. The pedagogical content is the training of a professional educator: 1) the basis of the training structure; 2) unifying components; 3) stimulating activities. Artistic and project specific features of the specialisation, methods and means of teaching.

In the formation of art-project competence, the discipline is system-forming, profiling, fundamentally aimed at the future. The particular importance of the stable core of the discipline, requires constant adjustment and updating [31].

In preparing the programme for the discipline, the following tasks are carried out:

1) The transformation of a social purpose, into a learning (pedagogical) purpose.

2) the pedagogical objective of student learning and development;

3) constructing the pedagogical process on the basis of scientific - content, methods, means and forms of learning. In order to improve the efficiency and quality of the educational process, the constant analysis of teaching material the selection of methods, forms and means to implement the development of students [32].

Data analysis.

Artistic project competence is realised through coordination, integration and amalgamation, developed by the American educator Benjamin Bloom on the basis of practice [33]. Coordination as the construction of

learning content structure based on knowledge from another field. Interdisciplinary links, implemented in the form of fragmented reference to common issues in different fields of knowledge. Integrative process, consistent with the methodology of the lessons. The programme material remains unchanged if necessary. For example, the use of material from other disciplines is possible in the History of Art classes. A labor-intensive integrative process requires combined programmes of various modifications:

1) Extended interdisciplinary programme. Linear interdisciplinary integration is carried out here:

2) Linking programme is the fusion of several disciplines, based on one systemic subject. Vertical integration is the process of studying profiling disciplines. The discipline "Artistic modelling" as an accumulating complex of components providing holistic formation of art-project competence is the profiling discipline.

3) A sequential programme is a strictly logical structure of teaching material, a form of implementation of a sequential programme called an integrated school day.

4) An amalgamated programme is the highest degree of integration. The basis is as close as possible to the real-life conditions of the project. Project-ideas are the most serious problems of modern design, training of teacher-designers, teaching design. The effectiveness of the process of formation of art-project competence of the future teacher of professional education in the field of design is increased in the process of learning activities into active professional activities.

Results

The notion of "professional competence of a design teacher" as the ability to carry out professional activities within mastered professional competences, enabling the implementation of knowledge, skills and personal qualities in the decision-making process necessary to carry out successful activities.

Artistic and design competence of a professional training teacher is a set of general cultural (general human) and professional (general and special professional) cultural competences, possessing a set of competences corresponding to professional activity guarantees the ability of a trainee to implement in practice the skills and knowledge obtained. The professional competence of a teacher of professional training in the field of design, which is a set of general cultural and professional competences, with artistic and creative competence of a teacher referred to professional (special) competences, is defined as the basic structure.

In order to determine the requirements for the content of training teachers of professional education in design, the artistic and design competence in the learning process is decomposed into the following components: artistic, design, personal, which allowed to substantiate the possibility of formation of the studied subject on the basis of systematization and integration, interdisciplinary interaction and complementarity of sectoral disciplines and special education, consistency and continuity in the development of teaching profession profession

The stages of constructing an integral structure of professional teachers' training content, including organizational and informational support, goal-setting, target value base determination, choice of a system-forming factor, choice of means and mechanisms oriented to the specificity of professional activity have been determined. It was revealed that according to the multifaceted orientation of art and design-creative activity of a higher school teacher in the field of design, the result of mastering the content of training should result in awareness of the social significance of design, activity and professional responsibility of the designer; knowledge of the basic regularities and patterns of science, technology, culture and art development; availability of practical skills in various types of fine arts, graphics, information technologies.

Discussion.

Qualitative training of a modern specialist requires modernization of the existing training system: bringing the information and content component of professional training in line with the level of professionalization, developing a mechanism for establishing not only interdisciplinary but also interdisciplinary links. The integrated structure of the learning content and the mechanisms of learning content for professional activities is based on the mechanisms of professional competence development, which are based on the principles of professional competence. The integrated structure of learning content harmonization mechanisms, "binary oppositions" is replaced by the notion of "components of integration". Reciprocal addition implies the possibility of the interpenetration of functions of structural elements of the content of professional training teacher training in the field of design [32].

The focus of the professional educator in the field of the art design, including art-project and psychological and pedagogical aspects, is provided by the combination of knowledge, skills and personal qualities that allow not only professional mastering of the laws of art and design creativity, but also implementation of teaching and training process.

Conclusion.

It has been revealed that in order to provide a high level of professional teacher training in the direction of "art-design" it is necessary to systematize and structure the subjects of the curriculum subject "design", "professional training (design)" on the principles of integration, interdisciplinarity and complementarity with orientation on the main subject, which in general aims to ensure the effectiveness of the educational process, focuses on preparing a competent specialist in the field of "art-design".

The research of the problem of formation of art-project competence is systemic, competence-based and integrated approach. The system of integral assessment of art-project competence formation is proposed.

A differentiated assessment methodology is needed to determine the readiness of a vocational educator in the art design profession.

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ПАТРИОТИЧЕСКИЕ ПЕСНИ АШУГА ДЖИВАНИ

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PATRIOTIC SONGS OF ASHUG JIVANI

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Статья посвящена патриотическим песням великого армянского ашуга Дживани (Серовбе Левонян – 1846-1909). В них нашли свое отражение, преобразование и развитие многие типичные элементы и принципы армянского национального музыкального мышления. Многие исследования показали, что в этом наследии развиваются важные элементы ближневосточной устной музыкально-поэтической традиции, а также проявляются глубокие элементы армянской народной песни, средневековой аллегории и духовной монодии, истоки и особенности национального самосознания. Этим объясняется высокие оценки современников и сегодняшняя большая популярность этих песен.

ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to the patriotic songs of the great Armenian ashug Jivani (Serovbe Levonyan - 1846-1909). They reflected, transformed and developed many typical elements and principles of the Armenian national musical thinking. Many studies have shown that important elements of the Middle Eastern oral musical and poetic tradition develop in this heritage, as well as deep elements of the Armenian folk song, medieval allegory and spiritual monody, the origins and features of national identity. This explains the high ratings of contemporaries and today's great popularity of these songs.

Ключевые слова: Александрополь, музыкальная жизнь, ашуг, жанр, традиционная музыка.

Keywords: Alexandropol, musical life, ashug, genre, traditional music.

Jivani was born in Kartsakh, near Akhalkalak, Georgia. He became an orphan when he was 8, his uncle looked after him. He learned music composition and performance on kamanche and violin with the support of master Ghara-Ghazar Siayi (Armenian: Չարս-Չարսը, Միսյի). In 1866 along with gusan Sazayi (Aghajan) Jivani moved to Tbilisi, where he continued his musical activities. The further development of Jivani's art is connected to Alexandropol (Gyumri) and its musical culture. He lived and worked there in 1868–

1895. In Alexandropol he headed a circle of fellow gusan-singers, and was awarded by the honorary title of ustabashi (leading master). Jivani had concerts all over Transcaucasia, including Batumi, Baku, Kars and Tbilisi. In 1895, he returned to Tbilisi.

Jivani was an author of more than 800 songs, written in romantic, ironical or realistic styles. He had the good knowledge of 19th century Armenian literature, and was influenced by it. He used clear forms of Armenian language, avoided of foreign transliterations. His